

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab

ESIL Working Groups Evaluation Report: Cohort 1, Year 1 (2024)

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Introduction

Program Description

The Environmental Data Science Innovation and Impact Lab (ESIIL, www.esiil.org) serves as a data science center of excellence and synthesis center that facilitates collaboration across large, interdisciplinary teams through the ESIIL Network. ESIIL enables a global community of environmental data scientists to leverage the wealth of environmental data and emerging analytics to develop science-based solutions to solve pressing challenges in biology and other environmental sciences. ESIIL's research community generates discoveries and novel approaches through 1) cutting-edge team science, 2) innovative tools and collaborative cyberinfrastructure, 3) data science education and training, and 4) building welcoming working groups. These activities advance the frontier of environmental data science, a rapidly evolving discipline bridging computational, biological, environmental, and social sciences.

ESIIL Working Groups: Working groups are self-organized research teams focused on well-defined scientific questions that advance environmental data science. Each year, teams respond to a call for proposals and the ESIIL leadership team selects a subset of groups to receive funding to carry out collaborative, interdisciplinary work over a period of two years. In 2023, ESIIL selected seven teams to join the first cohort of ESIIL Working Groups (WGs). Each group began their collaborations at an in-person meeting at the University of Colorado, Boulder for a 3-5 day meeting, with plans to continue working together throughout the year in virtual meetings. These groups met in Boulder between July 2024 and February 2025.

The WG evaluation included a pre-survey given before the in-person meeting began and a post, reflection survey at the end of the meeting. Six WGs chose to participate in these surveys, and one WG instead engaged in a group reflection with an evaluator at the end of the week (described in a separate report). This report describes the findings across the six Cohort 1 WGs who completed the pre/post surveys.

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation team used a collaborative approach (King and Stevahn 2013, Shulha et al. 2016) to develop the evaluation activities with the project leadership and coordinated with the Science of Team Science ESIIL team, led by Dr. John Parker. Working group members were invited to take an online pre-survey a few days before they arrived in Boulder, and they were sent an online post-survey on the last day of the in-person meeting.

ESIIL Program evaluation is co-led by Anne U. Gold, Megan K. Littrell, Emily Ward, and Abby McConnell. This study has been approved by the University of Colorado Institutional Research Board (IRB) Protocol 24-0222. Funding for this work was provided by the National Science Foundation (NSF, Award #DBI-2153040). This research was also supported in part by NOAA cooperative agreement NA22OAR4320151. *The statements, findings, conclusions, and recommendations are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of NSF, NOAA, or the U.S. Department of Commerce.*

Executive Summary

100% Of respondents were very (83%) or moderately (17%) **satisfied overall** with the in-person Working Group meeting.

100% Agreed or strongly agreed that they **felt respected** by their colleagues.

100% Agreed or strongly agreed that their Working Group members showed a general **respect for one another, respected the expertise of others** in the group, and the **contributions** of all group members **were valued**.

97% of respondents Agreed or Strongly Agreed they were motivated to **continue to work on the ideas that were explored** during the Working Group meeting.

47% of respondents reported engaging in other activities prior to their Working Group meeting, most often they participated in **Cyverse Discovery Environment Training (31%), Innovation Summit (22%), Cyberinfrastructure training (22%), and/or Cloud-based computing workstations training (20%)**.

Respondents saw a statistically significant **greater overlap between themselves and the EDS community at the end of the Working Group** than before the meeting ($Z = 2.00, p < .05$).

Respondents' Recommendations for Improving Working Group Meetings

Key Themes	Descriptions	Examples and Recommended Improvements
Personnel & Roles	Some respondents identified a need for clearer roles and more support from facilitators or external staff to improve the flow and productivity of sessions.	<p>"Having a dedicated note taker who was not invested in the discussion."</p> <p>"It would have been nice to interact with the ESIL staff and postdocs."</p> <p>"I think the meeting would've been more effective with timekeepers or more active facilitators that were not apart of the workshop..."</p> <p>"..maybe.. have more clearly defined roles going forward."</p>
Meeting Logistics & Venue	A few logistical issues were mentioned, including the hotel location, need for better pre-event planning, and concerns about burnout among Working Group PIs.	<p>"...the location of the hotel was not that great in terms of distance from the [meeting location]..."</p> <p>"Can ESIL staff prepare logistics for the working group beforehand (i.e., coordinating dinner reservations, ideas for out-of-office activities, etc.?)"</p> <p>"It's a lot of work to be the organizer. I wonder how much burnout there is among WG PIs."</p>
Reimbursement Structure	One key concern was the financial burden placed on attendees, with a suggestion to cover costs up front to ensure equitable participation.	<p>"We had one wg member who was not able to attend because having to pay for these costs was a financial burden."</p>

Respondents' Favorite Parts of the In-Person Working Group Meeting

Key Themes	Descriptions	Example Quotes
Overall Positive Experience	Many respondents expressed that the meeting was a worthwhile and uplifting experience, highlighting a sense of inclusivity and motivation from their group.	<i>"It was a good use of my time and pushed me as a science professional." "I felt welcomed and included in this group!" "[My] working group is creative and highly motivated... I look forward to the next workshop.."</i>
Collaborative Relationships & Group Cohesion	Many respondents emphasized how valuable it was to meet others, connect on a personal level, and build a sense of belonging with the group.	<i>"Building professional and personal relationships with the other group members over the course of the week and having super fun scientific discussions about big gaps in our field."</i>
Welcoming and Supportive Atmosphere	The tone and facilitation of the meeting stood out to some — the welcoming, lighthearted energy made it easier to engage.	<i>"This was my first formal, in-person WG meeting and I found the overall balance of professional but lighthearted approach mixed with a fun and inclusive atmosphere to be the most enjoyable aspect."</i>
Idea Generation & Scientific Exchange	A common highlight was collaborative brainstorming – generating research questions across disciplines, shaping deliverables, and exchanging scientific ideas.	<i>"I really liked the part about idea/question/deliverables generation. People from different research fields grouped together to express their opinions about phenology research." "Learning from my colleagues about different techniques. Socializing with new colleagues and networking."</i>
Productive Small Group Work	Respondents appreciated working in smaller, focused groups — whether for generating ideas, advancing tasks, or diving deep into discussion.	<i>"The back and forth between general brainstorming and small group work – we were able to progress on both the small and larger picture."</i>
Value of In-Person Engagement	Many respondents emphasized how meaningful in-person engagement was, especially compared to virtual meetings. emphasized how effective and energizing it was to meet face-to-face, especially for advancing goals and team dynamics.	<i>"Meeting in person and building group cohesion; getting full group buy-in on WG goals." "Having time to work together in the same space, discuss research ideas and plans, make progress on data products and research objectives."</i>

¹ Icons in the Executive Summary provided by the Noun Project's creators: Iconathon, Imam, Izwar Muis, Sitaresmi, Studio 365, Robert Chiaver, Thomas Le Bas, and Zuri.

Figure 2.

A large majority of respondents (**77%**) learned about the ESIL Working groups from **Word of Mouth (77%)**.

Figure 3.

Interest and Motivation to Join a Working Group

On the pre-survey, Working Group members were asked *What inspired you to apply to the ESILL Working Group call?* Table 1 provides a summary of responses:

Table 1

Key Themes	Highlights
Alignment with Expertise	Many respondents applied because the WG topic aligned with their research, and they wanted to contribute their expertise while also learning from others in their field.
Previous Positive Experience	Some respondents had attended past WGs at other centers and enjoyed the experience. Others noted attending the ESILL Innovation Summit and were impressed by the collaborative and dynamic environment.
Dedicated time & Resources	Respondents noted that the WG provided funding for computational resources, and structured time to focus on important research questions.
Passion for Team Science & Open Science	Respondents noted valuing team science and interdisciplinary collaboration, and were motivated by ESILL's mission of open, impactful science.
Learning & Skill Development	Many respondents were eager to develop computational and data science skills, including High-Performance computing (HPC), CyVerse, and knowledge-guided machine learning.
Professional Networking	Many respondents were directly invited to join by colleagues in similar research areas. Others noted that they wanted to work alongside and make new connections with others in the field.

On the pre-survey, Working Group members were asked *How would you describe the strengths that you bring to your Working Group?* Table 2 provides a summary of responses:

Table 2

Key Themes	Highlights
Data Science & Computational Skills	Many respondents noted general skills in statistical modeling & analysis, machine learning & AI, and programming expertise. Other respondents noted more specific skills, such as in remote sensing data, and expertise in cloud-computing systems like CyVerse and Jetstream2.
Domain Expertise & Scientific Knowledge	Many respondents highlighted their domain expertise as it related to the focus of their particular working group, and highlighted how their expertise would benefit the goals of their working group.
Research Collaboration & Facilitation Experience	A few respondents noted prior participation in synthesis working groups and successful co-facilitation, project management and leadership skills, experience synthesizing ideas and bridging gaps, and familiarity with open science.
Network & Outreach Expertise	Some respondents noted their strong connections within research communities as a benefit to the working group. Additionally, some noted experience in mentoring and outreach.
Conceptual Thinking & Synthesis	A few respondents highlighted their skills in linking key concepts and identifying research gaps, developing new frameworks and hypotheses, and creating thinking in research synthesis.
Soft Skills & Team science	Multiple respondents noted their strong organizational and people skills, ability to integrate diverse perspectives, and collaboration with inclusivity.

Respondent Demographic Information

Demographic data in this report were collected between June 2024 and February 2025, following NSF guidelines for demographic data collection at that time. The average survey response rate was 41%. Fifty-five percent of the Working Group (WG) members identified as Women and 44% as Men. Two percent of respondents preferred not to provide this information (Table 3).

The majority of respondents identified as White, Caucasian, European, or European American (61%). Respondents also identified as Asian or Asian American (26%); Hispanic, Latinx, or Hispanic or Latinx American (12%); Black, African American, or African (5%); or American Indian or Alaska Native (4%). Eight percent of respondents preferred not to answer, 6% selected more than one category, and 2% included a written response describing their race or ethnicity (Table 4).

Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation

A large majority of respondents (**78%**) had earned a **Doctoral degree**, **14%** held **Master’s degrees**, 4% had completed some graduate work, and 4% had a Bachelor’s degree (Table 5).

Table 3

Survey Respondent Gender	
55%	Women
43%	Men
2%	I prefer not to answer

Table 4 Survey Respondent Race and Ethnicity

61%	White, Caucasian, European, or European American
26%	Asian or Asian American
5%	Black, African American, or African
4%	American Indian or Alaska Native
12%	Hispanic, Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
8%	I prefer not to answer
4%	Middle Eastern or North African; Middle Eastern or North African American
2%	Not listed (<i>please specify</i>)
6%	More than one selection

Note. “More than one selection” and “Not listed” are not included in the total percentage because they both include multiple responses selected.

Table 5 Survey Respondents’ Highest Level of Education

78%	Doctoral degree
14%	Master’s degree
4%	Some graduate work
4%	Bachelor’s degree

Field of Study: Survey respondents were also asked to indicate the field in which they received their highest degree. These degrees encompassed a **diverse range of academic disciplines**, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of Environmental Data Science (EDS), with individuals from a wide array of fields contributing to the advancement and application of EDS (Table 6).

Table 6

Biological Sciences	Earth & Atmospheric Sciences	Environmental Sciences & Management	Interdisciplinary & Miscellaneous
Biology	Earth Science	Environmental Planning and Management	Astrophysics
Ecology	Meteorology	Environmental Science Policy & Management	Biogeochemistry
Genetics	Land and Atmospheric Sciences	Natural Resources	Geography
Wildlife Biology	Marine Science	Forest Resources	Geography & Environmental Studies
Aquatic Ecology			
Microbial Ecology			
Population Biology			
Zoology			
Plant Biology			
Plant Ecology			

Career Stage: **Twenty percent** of respondents were **students**, and just over a third of respondents (**39%**) described themselves as **Early Career** (0 – 5 years of professional experience or post-doctoral fellow). Thirty-three percent were Mid-Career (6 – 15 years of professional experience). Another 8% were at a Senior stage in their career (more than 15 years of experience). (Figure 4).

Figure 4.

Affiliation: Almost three-fourths of respondents work at an **Academic (higher education) institution (78%)**, followed by Federal Government agencies (22%), Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc.) organizations (8%), other non-profit organizations (6%), State Government agencies (4%), Industry (4%), K-12 or Informal Education (2%), Private for-profit (2%), Tribal organizations (2%), and Self-employed (2%). Six percent of respondents chose “Other” and reported being in retirement or employment with international organizations.

Academic Affiliations Represented. Of those respondents working at academic institutions, the majority reported affiliation with a **Research-Intensive institution (65%)**. Twenty-nine percent of academic affiliations included institutions serving both undergraduate and graduate students, 2% served primarily undergraduates, 4% included a professional program, and 4% included a community college. Some respondents also reported affiliation with a minority-serving institution (6%); a Hispanic-serving institution (10%); American and Native American Pacific Islander-serving institution (AAPISI; 6%) or a tribal college or university (4%) (Table 7).

Non-Academic Affiliations. Respondents who do not work for an academic institution described the main organization they are affiliated with. General categories representing these responses are listed below:

- National-scale ecological monitoring program
- Research contractor
- Federal science agency
- Independent climate research nonprofit
- National laboratory
- Federal environmental monitoring laboratory
- Government-affiliated environmental research institute

Disciplinary fields in EDS: The most commonly selected EDS fields selected by respondents included **Environmental Science (78%), Biological Science (55%), Artificial Intelligence (29%), Computer/Data Science (22%), and Geoscience (18%)**. Fewer respondents represented Social Sciences (6%), Math (4%), Chemistry/Biochemistry (4%), Engineering (2%) and Economics (2%). The majority of respondents selected more than one response as their main field in EDS. Open-ended “Other” responses (10%) included: Data Management, Forestry, Climate Change, and Ecology.

Professional Society Memberships: The list of memberships comprises a **wide range of professional societies**, including those related to ecology and natural science, geosciences and earth system sciences, freshwater and aquatic sciences, wildfire and fire ecology, microbiology, mycology, data science, conservation, and education and policy. Some societies are discipline-specific (e.g., Earth Science Information Partners, Mycological Society of America), while others are more broadly focused on fields like geophysics, earth sciences, and data science.

Table 7 Survey Respondent Academic Affiliations

69%	Research Intensive
18%	Undergraduate & Graduate student serving
8%	Primarily Undergraduate student serving
5%	Hispanic-Serving Institution
8%	Tribal College or University
5%	Minority-Serving Institution
3%	Community College/ 2-yr College

Several societies (e.g., American Geophysical Union and the Ecological Society of America) appeared multiple times in the list, indicating their prominence and potential popularity among professionals.

Accommodation Requests

The pre-survey asked respondents to describe any accommodation needs. Seven people provided responses to this question. Table 8 provides a summary of themes and representative verbatim quotes.

Table 8

Key Themes	Example Quotes
Anxiety and ADHD Accommodations	<i>"I appreciated the 'worry stones' or fidget gadgets from [previous events]; helped with my social anxiety..."</i>
Break & Rest Spaces	<i>"quiet spaces to take breaks in."</i>
Visual Accessibility	<i>"Font sizes need to be big enough to read."</i>
Medical & Dietary Accommodations	<i>"Sugar free sweeteners, disclosure of nutritional information when possible... ability to take breaks during meetings to hydrate, blood glucose check, and administer medications..."</i>
Childcare Support	<i>"the working group I will be participating in will offer child care support. Without it, I would not have been able to attend."</i>
Virtual Participation Needs	<i>"As I do not have a travel grant, I shall be attending virtually."</i>
Language Access	<i>"[accommodate the] language barrier."</i>

Working Group Evaluation Outcomes

Satisfaction with the ESIL Working Group In-Person Meeting

One hundred percent of respondents were **satisfied** with the in-person ESIL Working Group meeting overall (83% "Very Satisfied;" 17% "Moderately Satisfied").

The majority of respondents (**71%**) were **Very** or **Moderately Satisfied** with the **computational resources and assistance** provided and that **Cyberinfrastructure was easy to use (64%)**. Thirty-three percent of respondents agreed that they were satisfied with Slack as a way to communicate. However, 38% indicated that this was not applicable for their group (Figure 5).

Most respondents **Agreed** or **Strongly Agreed** that:

- **communication** about the meeting **was effective (98%)**,
- the **goals** of sessions were **clearly communicated (98%)**,
- the meeting was **well planned** and **well facilitated**, and the **agenda was well-designed (93% each)**,
- the **social activities** were appropriate (**91%**),
- **speakers and presenters were engaging (86%)**, and
- the **food** provided was good (**68%**) (Figure 6).

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Highlights and Areas for Improvement of the In-person Working Group Meetings

The best parts of the ESIL Working Group meetings, according to respondents, can be summarized into the following key themes:

Table 9

Key Themes	Description	Example Quote
Building Relationships & Group Cohesion	Many respondents emphasized how valuable it was to meet others, connect on a personal level, and build a sense of belonging with the group.	<i>“Building professional and personal relationships with the other group members over the course of the week and having super fun scientific discussions about big gaps in our field.”</i>
Brainstorming & Idea Generation	A common highlight was collaborative brainstorming – generating research questions, shaping deliverables, and exchanging scientific ideas.	<i>“I really liked the part about idea/question/deliverables generation. People from different research fields grouped together to express their opinions about phenology research.”</i>
Breakout Sessions & Small Group Work	Respondents appreciated working in smaller, focused groups — whether for generating ideas, advancing tasks, or diving deep into discussion.	<i>“The back and forth between general brainstorming and small group work – we were able to progress on both the small and larger picture.”</i>
Cross-disciplinary Exchange	Some valued the chance to learn about new techniques, models, and perspectives from other researchers.	<i>“Learning from my colleagues about different techniques. Socializing with new colleagues and networking.”</i>
In-Person Interaction	Many respondents emphasized how meaningful in-person engagement was, especially compared to virtual meetings.	<i>“Meeting in person and building group cohesion; getting full group buy-in on WG goals.”</i>
Supportive and Fun Atmosphere	The tone and facilitation of the meeting stood out to some — the supportive and lighthearted energy made it easier to engage.	<i>“This was my first formal, in-person WG meeting and I found the overall balance of professional but lighthearted approach mixed with a fun and inclusive atmosphere to be the most enjoyable aspect.”</i>
Concrete Progress Toward Goals	A number of respondents highlighted the ability to make real progress on data, models, or shared research goals.	<i>“Having time to work together in the same space, discuss research ideas and plans, make progress on data products and research objectives.”</i>

Respondents also shared challenges of the Working Group meetings, summarized in the table below:

Table 10

Key Themes	Description	Example Quote
Reaching Consensus & Research Direction	Many found it challenging to align hypotheses, methods, and overall direction — especially with diverse disciplinary perspectives or limited time.	<i>“Nailing down the hypotheses and agreeing on a research direction. This is, of course, the whole point of a working group but in the moment, it can feel like a slog.”</i>
Group Dynamics & Leadership Challenges	Several mentioned struggles with leadership roles, delegation, or team coordination.	<i>“I had hoped my co-leads would step up more, but not all of them did, which felt hard.”</i>
Communication Across Disciplines or Teams	Disciplinary divides, different vocabularies, and misaligned group knowledge were a barrier for some.	<i>“I found that the most challenging part was having each contingent understand the other, both in terms of terminology and concepts.”</i>
Mental Fatigue	A common theme was difficulty staying mentally energized, especially during long days with few breaks.	<i>“Being present when I'm exhausted.”</i>
Time Constraints & Pacing	The meeting felt either too short to accomplish goals or packed in a way that created time pressure or uneven pacing.	<i>“Two days went by very fast; and the days were short.”</i>
Technical or Logistical Issues	Some respondents faced technical issues, unclear demos, or felt that setup/logistics took away from productivity.	<i>“The technical demos were not as useful as I'd hoped because most of the participants were not prepared to use CyVerse.”</i>
Financial & Accessibility Barriers	Respondents noted the financial burden of attending and concerns about inclusivity for students or international participants.	<i>“It is challenging having to have to pay out of pocket all of the meeting costs...”</i>
Personal Confidence & Impostor Syndrome	Especially for students or early-career folks, being in a room with more senior respondents could feel intimidating.	<i>“Being a graduate student in a room of professors was intimidating... I felt I wasn't making a significant contribution.”</i>
Virtual Participation Challenges	Remote respondents struggled to follow complex in-person discussions and felt more limited in engagement.	<i>“Following some of the conversation virtually... I am not a very good auditory learner.”</i>

Motivation to Continue Collaborations and Research

97% of respondents left the meeting feeling **largely motivated to continue working on the ideas they explored during the meeting**, with 80% indicating being motivated *To a Very Large Extent*, 18% *To a Large Extent*, and 3% *To a Moderate Extent*.

Respondents were asked to elaborate on their motivation to continue working on the ideas that were explored during their meeting. Table 11 provides a summary of responses:

Table 11

Key Themes	Descriptions
Alignment with Personal Research Interests	Many respondents noted that the topics overlapped with their existing research or thesis work, fueling intrinsic motivation.
Clear Plans with Tangible Next Steps	Motivation was higher when respondents left with a well-defined plan, deliverables, writing tasks, or scheduled meetings.
Exciting and Novel Ideas or Datasets	Exposure to new datasets, tools, or research questions made respondents eager to dive in, and some reported being motivated by seeing real potential for publishable outputs or grant proposals.
Strong Group Dynamics	Being a part of a cohesive, respectful, and enthusiastic group inspired people to contribute.
Opportunities for Collaboration	Respondents noted that working with new people, especially across disciplines, was a strong motivator. Respondents noted looking forward to continued engagement with collaborators that they ‘clicked’ with.
Personal and Professional Growth	Respondents who reported being early-career and having the chance to co-author papers with potentially more senior researchers was a major driver to continue the work.

Participants’ Perspectives on Being EDS Professionals

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted to evaluate changes in respondents’ pre-survey and reflection survey responses about how they identify with being a member of the EDS community. Before and after the Working Groups, respondents were asked to *Choose the picture that best described the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community*. Results showed a significant change such that **respondents saw a greater overlap between themselves and the EDS community at the end of the Working Group meeting** compared to before the meeting ($Z = 2.00, p < .05$), (Figure 8).

Additionally, **80% of respondents** who **transitioned out of selection “E”** on the pre-survey moved up into **selection “F”** on the post-survey. If moving up one letter choice is *1 point* (e.g., transitioning from “E” before the meeting to “F” after), respondents saw an average **increase of .56 points**. Additionally, **18% more respondents** selected figures showing **half or more overlap between the self and the EDS Community (selections E-G)** after the Working Group in comparison to *before*.

Figure 8.

Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Respondents were also asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with statements about their sense of belonging in the EDS community. Respondents' agreement significantly changed from pre- to post-survey for:

- **“I belong to the EDS Community”** ($Z = 2.25, p = .024$; a 25% increase in agreement),
- **“Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity”** ($Z = 3.16, p = .001$; a 37% increase in agreement), and
- **“There is a strong feeling of belonging among my Working Group (WG) members”** ($Z = 3.10, p = .002$; a 43% increase in agreement) (Figure 9).

Figure 9.

In a final open-ended question, respondents were asked to *Please share any other feedback you have about the Working Group Meeting*. Themes and representative verbatim responses are included below in Table 12.

Table 12

Key Themes	Description	Example Quote
Positive Experiences & Gratitude	Many respondents expressed appreciation for the event’s collaborative, welcoming, and motivating environment.	<i>"It was amazing; such a bright and positive group of scientists! I love working groups, and ESIL and our group leaders did a wonderful job making our first Fungal Dispersal working group meeting a great experience."</i>
Facilitation & Structure Needs	Some suggested improvements to meeting structure, like clearer roles, timekeeping, or having dedicated facilitators to support smoother flow.	<i>"The meeting would've been even more effective with timekeepers or more active facilitators that were not part of the workshop... Some discussions were rushed because of the time creeping up on us."</i>
Logistical Challenges	Respondents noted issues with hotel location, rideshare costs, and a desire for more convenient lodging or better advance notice.	<i>"The location of the hotel was not that great in terms of distance from the SEEC and also the distance from nearby markets and eateries."</i>
Financial Accessibility	Some indicated that paying for members’ travel expenses upfront would help more participants to be able to participate in the meeting.	<i>"Can ESIL work to provide international participants flight and hotel costs upfront...? Funding these upfront would increase the inclusive nature of working groups."</i>
Leadership Burnout	There were concerns about workload and burnout for organizers and leads, especially when logistical support was limited.	<i>"It's a lot of work to be the organizer. I wonder how much burnout there is among WG PIs."</i>
Team Culture & Impact	A few respondents highlighted how meaningful the working group was for participants’ careers and community building.	<i>"I really enjoyed this working group and think it will have an important impact in my career moving forward."</i>

Team Science Findings

ESIL Science of Team Science Lead, Dr. John Parker, and Post-doctoral Researcher Kayleigh Ward included a series of survey items on the pre-Summit and post-Summit reflection surveys. Their findings and interpretations are included below.

Group Dynamics: Collaboration and Creativity

Data on working group composition and collaborative dynamics can be roughly divided into four main dimensions: (1) diversity of expertise; (2) progress and creativity; (3) psychological safety; (4) and balanced participation.

The synthesis center working group model is based on convening research groups with diverse forms of expertise and experience to integrate disparate forms of knowledge in service of science, policy, and society. Thus, as expected, around **90%** of ESIL working group members **agreed or strongly agreed** that group members **varied widely in their expertise and backgrounds** while sharing similar values (Figure 10). Such expertise, combined with similar values, helps to support the convergent forms of scientific creativity at which synthesis groups aim (Harvey, 2013; 2014).

Working group members also believed that they made progress and were creative. Across groups, **95%** of survey respondents **agreed or strongly agreed** that **the group was creative, worked well together, and made progress**, indicating their sense that their group was moving forward in creative ways that advanced their collective goals (Figure 11).

Figure 10.

Figure 11.

The same is true of group members' perceptions of **psychological safety**, referring to group cultures in which individuals feel free to express their thoughts and feelings, take appropriate risks, and openly express themselves without negative consequences. Psychological safety is key for enabling group creativity as it allows for free flow of ideas, amicable disagreement, and tentative expression of unorthodox thinking that may lead to creative advances without fear of censure or judgement by other group members (Reiter-Palmon & Miller, 2023; Parker, In press). **Greater than 95% of group members felt respected by colleagues, felt comfortable providing opposing viewpoints, and believed that group members showed respect for one another** (Figure 12).

Figure 12.

Group members also indicated that in general there was **balanced participation** within the group in terms of everyone being able to express their ideas and that these ideas were valued. This is critical in synthesis groups whose main purpose is to elicit and integrate information and perspectives from a diverse group of researchers and is a critical element of group creativity (Reidl et al., 2021; Parker et al., 2020). All respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the **contributions of all members were valued (100%)**, and that all members had **adequate time to express their ideas (86%)** (Figure 13). While about a quarter believed that **certain members dominated the discussion (23%)**, this is common, particularly as groups become larger (Bernard & Mize, 2016; Parker, In press). Responses in this category indicate that the ESILL working groups accommodated a wide range of inputs from across the working groups.

Figure 13.

Additionally, respondents were invited to elaborate on their response regarding to what extent the working group fostered creativity. Below is a summary of their responses:

Key Themes	Descriptions
Diversity of Expertise & Perspectives	Respondents appreciated interacting with people from different disciplines, backgrounds, and toolkits. This interdisciplinary exchange helped spark new ideas and reveal new approaches.
Collaboration and Shared Enthusiasm	Enthusiasm and mutual excitement across working groups boosted creativity. Additionally, good relationships among working group members were noted as fostering open communication that helped people feel comfortable sharing novel thoughts.
Adequate Time to Develop Ideas	Respondents noted having ample time to allow ideas to evolve, and opportunities to present ideas early and refine them based on feedback helped creativity grow.
Small Group Discussions and Breakouts	Breakout sessions were repeatedly described as particularly creative or assisting in creative idea generation. These smaller formats enabled idea-bouncing and deeper conversations.
Cutting-edge Tools	Multiple respondents noted that using new tools such as AI or deep learning to address old problems created space for innovation.
Multimedia Usage	Working groups were use of various media to communicate helped encourage some to feel more expressive and innovative.

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Appendix A: Evaluation Surveys

ESIL Working Group Pre-survey

Which Working Group are you part of?

- Fungal Dispersal traits
- AI for Natural Methane
- Modeling Extreme Wildfires
- BioViewPoint
- Macrophenology
- EDS for Maka Sitomniya
- Worldwide FreshH2O Zoops

How did you learn about ESIL Working Groups? Select all that apply.

- I attended the ESIL Innovation Summit.
- I participated in an ESIL Hackathon or Codefest event
- I received an email from ESIL@colorado.edu.
- LinkedIn
- Twitter/X
- ESIL's website
- Word of Mouth - I heard from others about it
- An online forum or Slack channel (e.g. ECOLOG, AISES)
 - If so, which one: _____
- Other: _____

Which of the following ESIL activities have you participated in? Select all that apply.

- Innovation Summit
- Hackathon or CodeFest
- Another Working Group
- AI skills training
- Cyberinfrastructure training
- Cyverse Discovery Environment Training
- Cloud-based computing workstations training
- R & Python bilingualism training
- Environmental Science and Data Cubes training
- ESIL Stars or EDS Core training
- Cultural Intelligence training
- Other _____
- I have not participated in other ESIL activities.

What inspired you to apply to the ESIL Working Group call?

Did you collaborate with any of the Working Group members before you joined the Working Group?

- Yes
- No

If Yes: Please list the names of the Working Group members you have worked with before.

Working Group Member #1 *_example: Emily Ward* _____

Working Group Member #2 _____

Working Group Member #3 _____

[Skip Logic - display only when “yes”] For each of the other working group members that you already collaborated with, Please indicate the nature of the collaboration with [Name-- repeats for each name provided]. (Select all that apply)

Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with **Emily Ward** (Select all that apply)*

- Ongoing research
- Grant proposals for future research
- Co-author on papers
- Collaboration on data products
- Collaboration on code or software tools
- Collaboration on educational materials
- Preliminary discussions
- Learning
- Other (please explain)

How would you describe the strengths (such as skills, relevant expertise) that you are bringing to your Working Group?

You completed an application for the Working Group that included questions about your expertise and expectations for the working group. Is it okay with you if we include your application responses in this evaluation study? (Data will be de-identified after the data collection period ends.)

- Yes
- No

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science (EDS) when answering the next few questions: We define EDS broadly to include any work where large datasets are used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences. We are interested in learning about how your participation in an ESILL Working Group is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					
There is a strong feeling of belonging among my Working Group team members.	<input type="radio"/>					

Which of the following best describes your current career stage?

- Student (I am an undergraduate student or graduate student)
- Early Career (I am a post-doctoral fellow or have 0 to 5 years of professional experience.)
- Mid-Career (I have 6 to 15 years of professional experience.)
- Senior (I have more than 15 years of professional experience.)
- Other. Please describe. _____
- Prefer not to answer.

What best describes the organization in which you work?

- Academic (higher education)
- Government: Federal
- Government: State
- Government: Local
- Industry
- K-12 or Informal Education
- Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc)
- Non-profit: other
- Private for-profit
- Tribal organization
- Self
- Other: _____
- Prefer not to answer

Are you affiliated with an academic institution?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = Yes

With which type of academic institution are you affiliated? Select all that apply.

- Community College/ 2-yr College
- Professional Program
- American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AAPISI)
- Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI)
- Historically Black University (HBCU)
- Tribal College or Tribal-Serving Institution (TCU)
- Minority Serving Institution (MSI)
- Primarily Undergraduate Serving
- Undergraduate and Graduate Serving
- Research Intensive (R1/R2/etc)
- If none of the options fit, how would you describe the main academic institution you are affiliated with? _____
- Prefer not to answer

Please name the organization(s) you work for: _____

Which of the following categories best describes your highest level of education?

- Some high school
- High school diploma or equivalent
- Vocational training
- Some college
- Associate degree (e.g. AA, AE, AFA, AS, ASN)
- Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BBA, BFA, BS)
- Some graduate work
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MBA, MFA, MS, MSW)
- Applied or professional graduate degree (e.g. MD, DDS, JD)
- Doctoral degree (e.g. EdD, PhD)
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

In what field and in what year did you receive your highest degree?

What are(is) the main professional societies(y) to which you belong? Please select up to 5 professional societies from the drop-down menu, or type in the organization's full name.

- Other (please specify) _____
- Prefer not to answer

In which disciplinary field(s) of Environmental Data Science do you MAINLY work? Select all that apply.

- Artificial Intelligence/ Machine Learning
- Chemistry/ Biochemistry
- Computer/Data Science
- Biological science
- Economics
- Engineering
- Environmental Science
- Geoscience (Geology, Geography)
- Math
- Social Science
- Other. Please specify. _____
- Prefer not to answer
- I don't work in an EDS field.

Where do you live?

- I live in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:) _____
- I am outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?) _____
- I prefer not to answer

Where is your place of work located?

- Place of work is in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code)___
- Place of work within a Tribal Nation (If yes, please list the Tribal Nation) _____
- Place of work is outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?) _____
- I prefer not to answer

ESIL Working Group Reflection Survey

Which Working Group are you part of?

- AI for Natural Methane
- BioViewPoint
- EDS for Maka Sitomniya
- Fungal Dispersion
- Macrophenology
- Modeling Extreme Wildfires
- Worldwide FreshH2O Zoops

What were the best parts about the Working Group meeting?

What were the most challenging parts of the Working Group meeting?

Overall, how satisfied were you with the Working Group meeting?

- Very Satisfied
- Moderately Satisfied
- Neutral
- Moderately Dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied

How satisfied were you with the following parts of the Working Group meeting

	Very Satisfied	Moderately Satisfied	Neutral	Moderately Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	N/A
Cyberinfrastructure ease of use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Computational resources and assistance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Slack as a way to communicate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about the logistics for the Work Group meeting, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Communication about the meeting was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meeting was well-planned	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Goals of sessions were clearly communicated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meeting was well-facilitated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agenda was well-designed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food provided was good	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speakers and presenters were engaging	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social activities (dinner, walk) were appropriate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Have you made new connections or research collaborations during the meeting? If so, please elaborate

Thinking about the Working Group meeting overall, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Colleagues showed a general respect for one another	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Colleagues respected the expertise of others in the group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The contributions of all group members were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagreements were handled constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting code of conduct was consistently implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about your own experiences during the meeting, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
I felt respected by my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others in my group respected my expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt my contributions were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I handled disagreements constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was creative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Working Group environment as you experienced it during this meeting?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
My working group is similar with regard to its cultural background	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my working group share similar values	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my working group have a variety of different backgrounds and experiences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Members of my working group vary widely in their areas of expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All working group members had adequate time to express their ideas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Certain working group members dominated the discussion	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The working group's diversity contributed to its effectiveness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The group was creative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The group worked well together	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The group made progress	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent did the Working Group meeting foster creativity?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

Please elaborate on your answer to the previous question

To what extent are you motivated to continue working on the ideas that were explored during the meeting?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

Please elaborate on your answer to the previous question

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences. We are interested

in learning about how your participation in the Working Group is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community

Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					
There is a strong feeling of belonging among my Working Group members	<input type="radio"/>					

Please describe any new **data skills, tools, or workflows** that you learned about throughout the Working Group Meeting (if any).

Please provide two responses for each statement to tell us **how confident you feel** in doing these tasks independently **AFTER you finished participating** in the Working Group Meeting **compared to BEFORE participating** in the Working Group Meeting.

	CONFIDENCE AFTER					CONFIDENCE BEFORE				
	Very Confident	Moderately Confident	Slightly Confident	Not Confident	N/A	Very Confident	Moderately Confident	Slightly Confident	Not Confident	N/A
Interpreting Python code	<input type="radio"/>									
Working with data cubes and data libraries	<input type="radio"/>									
Creating reproducible workflows	<input type="radio"/>									
Running code in the cloud	<input type="radio"/>									
Documenting code so others can use it	<input type="radio"/>									
Collaborating with new people	<input type="radio"/>									
Coding with other people	<input type="radio"/>									

Please share any other feedback you have about the Working Group meeting
